

D8.1 Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plan at EU & national level

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Please note that the review of this document is still in progress, and the deliverable is subject to final approval. Any feedback or changes provided during this review process may affect the final version, and approval from the relevant parties is required before the deliverable is considered complete.

List of Abbreviations

AC	Associated Countries
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
CFD	Climate Farm Demo
CoDIE	Co-Design Innovation Experiment
CoP	Community of Practice
CS	Climate Smart
CSA	Climate Smart Advisor
(CS-)AKIS	(Climate Smart) Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
(CS-)AS	(Climate Smart) Advisory Services
(CS)-ASP	(Climate Smart) Advisory Service Providers
CSC	Climate Smart Coach
CSF	Climate Smart Farming
DEC	Dissemination, exploitation and communication
DLA	Dynamic Learning Agenda
GA	General Assembly
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
MA	Multi-Actor
ME&L	Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning
MIP	Multi-Sector Innovation Project
MS	Member States
NC	National Coordinator
PA	Practice Abstracts
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
PDF	Pilot Demonstration Farm
PIP	Projects, Flagship Initiatives and Policy Makers
TL	Thematic Leader
TTT	Train the Trainer

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1 Abstract

Deliverable D8.1 introduces the Dissemination, Exploitation, & Communication (DEC) Plan, a strategic roadmap meticulously designed to identify, elaborate upon, and execute a robust communication and dissemination strategy. This strategy encompasses the sharing of project results and knowledge on both European and national scales, targeting the extensive EU agricultural advisory community and other pertinent actors and stakeholders throughout the EU and AC regions.

This is the first version of the plan, submitted in M6 of the project. The primary aim is to successfully promote project activities, disseminate results and outputs, and exploit knowledge, approaches, and solutions developed within the project. The project further raises awareness of the importance of boosting the role of agricultural advisors and ASPs by strengthening their capacity to provide targeted advice, implement the approaches, and share the solutions developed in ClimateSmartAdvisors (CSA) on a wider scale.

Within this document, we detail an array of communication tools and channels meticulously crafted to bolster the achievement of our DEC objectives. These encompass a project website, a spectrum of social media channels, both external and internal newsletters, visual identity elements, and a host of other strategic resources. Importantly, this document is a dynamic, evolving resource, slated for two revisions: one at Month 24 (D8.2) and another at Month 48 (D8.3). These planned revisions enable us to continuously re-evaluate and enhance our approach, ensuring its ongoing effectiveness.

As the leader of WP8 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication, the BioSense Institute (BIOS) will lead the implementation of the DEC strategy with support from all project partners. A plan for monitoring & evaluation will be used to follow the progress and quality of DEC activities, which are designed to allow CSA partners to disseminate their results and engage with stakeholders.

2 Introduction

ClimateSmartAdvisors is a pan-European multi-actor network covering 27 countries. Its aim is to boost the EU agricultural advisory community, leading to an acceleration of the adoption of climate smart (CS) farming practices by the wider farming community within and across EU AKISs. To reach this objective, ClimateSmartAdvisors focuses on the crucial role of advisors in the development and dissemination of CS innovations and practices. The project will organize activities focusing on strengthening the advisors' capacity to provide CS advice and boosting the advisors' role in the transition towards CS farming through their involvement in innovation projects, CS-AKIS, and EU projects and initiatives.

The project activities will support the establishment of an EU-wide network of 260 advisory Communities of Practice (CoP) to support peer-to-peer knowledge exchange for 1500 advisors (the core of CSA). In support of this, 140 advisors (so-called Climate Smart Coaches) will receive expert training on CoP facilitation, and on selected CS topics across 12 thematic areas. The DEC strategy, deployed at EU and national levels, will support all other Work Packages (WPs) in promoting all project activities, and it will accelerate the wide spread of results.

The current submission provides a comprehensive explanation of the chosen strategies, tools, and communication channels tailored to suit this project's approach in disseminating, communicating, and leveraging its results. Ongoing refinements are anticipated, with two planned revisions in M24 and M48. Additionally, the document includes directives on maintaining the project's visual identity and effectively leveraging social media to engage various target audiences.

3 Objectives and target audience

3.1 Project objectives

Climate Smart Advisors' overall aim is to mobilise the EU agricultural advisory community, leading to an acceleration of the adoption of CSF practices by the wider farming community within and across EU AKISs, and boost the role of agricultural advisors and ASP by strengthening their capacity in providing targeted advice and by implementing the approaches and sharing the solutions developed in ClimateFarmDemo (CFD) on a wider scale, across MS and AC.

Number	CSA Specific Objectives
O1	To connect advisors and ASP across EU MS and associated countries to the CFD pilot demonstration farm network, to grow the network, and support peer learning between advisors, both on impactful advisory methods and CSF practices.
O2	To deliver a CSF Train-the-Trainer (TTT) type training module, and support the delivery of CSF training seminars across partner countries, resulting in an enhancement of the capacity of both current and future farm advisors to empower EU farmers in climate action.
O3	To understand and support the role of advisors in CSF MIPs and CS-AKIS across Europe, to identify and address gaps in CSF advisory activities in MIPs, and to deliver tools and materials for a wide range of CSA types to better participate in CSF innovation activities.
O4	To monitor and evaluate the capacity building and learning within the CSA network and improve its functioning and impact in strengthening advisors to accelerate the adoption of CSF practices.
O5	To build a supportive toolkit for CSCs & CSAs and for the wider advisory community. This should consist of good farm practices, assessment tools, advisory, training, and teaching methods, adapted to CSF and carbon topics and to the diversity of EU situations, embedded in an interactive repository.
O6	To engage and empower key actors within regional/national AKIS and across MS in supporting CS-AS and creating an enabling environment for its implementation.
O7	To build a network of related EU Projects, EU flagship initiatives, and policy makers (PIPs) (at EU and national levels) to create project visibility and cooperation, integrate research and knowledge from other projects, produce common policy and operational recommendations, and prepare a sustainability strategy for the whole CSA network. Corresponding WPs: WP7
O8	To develop a strong communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy to ensure that knowledge and project results are communicated and disseminated to the EU agricultural advisory community and all other relevant actors and stakeholders across the EU & AC.

Table 1 Project objectives

3.2 DEC objectives

The overall project objective is to widely communicate, disseminate, and exploit innovative solutions for the adoption of CSF practices by the wider farming community within and across EU AKISs.

The main objective of the CSA project's Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication is to set up and maintain a specifically designed strategy and network to i) promote the project and its results among the 74 organisations in 27 countries, as well as external stakeholders, and wider audience; ii) disseminate learnings, tools, and other relevant information to the wider EU advisory community, using different channels, and iii) utilise project results in further research and networking activities beyond the CSA project.

3.3 CSA target audience & description

A precise definition and thorough understanding of the target audience serve as the foundation for enhancing the project's outreach efforts. This comprehension enables us to

tailor our communication to resonate specifically with the individuals we aim to connect with. Effective communication transcends merely transmitting a message; it revolves around delivering the precise message to the precise audience.

When the audience isn't accurately defined or the messages aren't thoughtfully crafted, there's a risk that the project won't strike a chord with its intended recipients. By gaining insights into these target groups, our DEC activities can be personalized to better align with the audience's needs and interests. This, in turn, leads to increased engagement rates and amplifies the overall efficiency and effectiveness of our communication strategy.

Target group	Description
Agricultural advisors and advisory services	The project will bring together 1,500 well-trained advisors from 27 countries, and involved in 260 CoPs. These advisors, including CSCs and CSAs, will use training materials and tools developed by the project to help farmers implement climate-friendly practices. CSCs will receive training in three key areas (facilitation skills for CoP operation, networking with local CS-AKIS actors, and adopting suitable local advisory methods and tools), and once they are trained, they will be sharing their experiences, and providing feedback to improve the training programmes. These trained advisors will not only assist farmers but also encourage their fellow advisors to promote these practices. This will create a ripple effect of peer-to-peer learning, modeling, and training, leading to broader adoption of climate-smart farming techniques.
Farmers	The project will connect to the 1500 Pilot Demo Farmers from the CFD project who will benefit from both projects, and will lead to empowering empower EU farmers in climate action. Moreover, through 100 videos produced and content added to the Knowledge repository that feeds the Platform developed together with the CFD project, results of the project will be accessible to large community of farmers across the continent.
Research and education	The consortium involves applied research organisations and research institutes and universities, which will work in multi-actor partnerships on knowledge generation. The project will have an impact on a wider research community across Europe by increasing the capacity of researchers to perform future development, monitoring, and evaluation of effective CS advisory tools and CSF practices.
EIP Agri Service Point and CAP Networks	The project will partner with 24 National CAP Networks to increase communication in the national AKIS and promote different event/ that will take place throughout the project.
Policy makers	The project will foster meaningful dialogues with policymakers at various levels, including national ministries, policy makers on EU level ((EC DGAGRI, DGENV, DGCLIMA, DGRI, EUFRD, EP), and local authorities, to ensure decision makers receive information „from the field“ that will help them better design and evaluate policies.

Table 2 Target groups description

4 Communication strategy

The communication strategy establishes the foundation for effective communication of a project, its objectives and ambition. Moreover, communication actions continuously complement dissemination and exploitation efforts, spanning the entirety of the CSA project from inception to completion. We aim to effectively engage our main stakeholder groups by employing the strategic guidelines outlined in the Table 3, with a strong emphasis on tailoring our approach to suit different project phases, various situations, and contexts.

Target group	Interest / Need	Means of outreach
Agricultural advisors and advisory services	<p>Interested in acquiring additional knowledge about CSF practices and advisory approaches to boost their capacity in assisting farmers and enhancing the sustainability of their farming businesses within the realm of climate-smart agriculture.</p> <p>Furthermore, eager to enhance the role of advisors in both national and regional CS-AKIS while aligning with the objectives of the CAP.</p>	<p>Tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge repository Online training platform Practice abstracts Flyers Press release articles Annual Award for inspiring CSA practice <p>Channels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project website Project social media networks External newsletter Agricultural journals and magazines International conferences organised by the project EIP Agri Service Point and CAP Networks Relevant national and EU Repositories (e.g. FarmDemo, EUFarmBook).
Farmers	Eager to receive customized, hands-on guidance for implementing CSF practices and exploring potential rewarding mechanisms.	<p>Tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge repository Print material: posters, flyers Video materials <p>Channels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advisors Agricultural fairs Social media (especially Facebook) Farmers' associations Agricultural magazines, journals and portals TV/radio EIP Agri Service Point and CAP Networks Demonstrations
Research and education	<p>Eager to engage in collaborative multi-actor partnerships that expedite the development of impactful CSF practices. Additionally, interested in educating students about the pivotal role of CSAs in the journey toward achieving climate-neutral farming.</p> <p>Enthusiastic about academic content, including publications, scientific posters, and conference presentations.</p>	<p>Tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge repository Scientific posters Open science publications <p>Channels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project website and social media (especially LinkedIn) International conferences organised by the project Participation to topic-related conferences

Target group	Interest / Need	Means of outreach
		Scientific journals
EIP Agri Service Point and CAP Networks	Interested in enhancing recognition and bolstering support from regional and national CS-AKIS to advance the delivery of more effective Advisory Services with a focus on CSF practices. Keen to foster collaborative multi-actor innovation partnerships both at the European and national levels within the AKIS.	Tools: Practice abstracts Channels: Project website Project social media networks
Policy makers	Interested in receiving concrete results and evidence-backed recommendations that illuminate the impact pathways. Enthusiastic about actively participating in events, demonstrations, networking opportunities, and engaging in meaningful face-to-face dialogues.	Tools: Policy briefs Channels: Project website Bilateral meetings TV/radio

Table 3 Interests/Needs of the target groups and means of outreaching

Although the context and channel affect the messages we aim to convey to captivate the attention of the specific audience, this communication strategy offers the framework with overarching messages for each distinct target group that can be found in table below.

Target group	Key messages
Agricultural advisors and advisory services	Enhance support, advice,, and empowerment to EU farmers in climate action by leveraging relevant, tailored CS training modules. Get involved in the CoP network to exchange knowledge. Increase your capacity to navigate the transition towards CSF approaches. Participate in CoDIESs and take on the role of a change and innovation agent in CSF multilevel transitions.
Farmers	Through the integration of adaptation and mitigation strategies aimed at curbing greenhouse gas emissions and bolstering carbon sequestration within ecosystems, your farm can achieve heightened sustainability. Benefit from tailored advice and innovative tools to reduce your climate impact. Be rewarded for your climate smart practices and ensure an economically viable business.
Research and education	Co-create new solutions with a wide range of stakeholders engaged in sustainable transitions. Teach new generations about the role of advisors in facilitating transitions towards CSF.
EIP Agri Service Point and CAP Networks	Disseminate knowledge on CS-AS and the optimal role of advisors in MIPs. Improve recognition of and support from regional/national CS-AKISs for implementing better AS focusedn CSF practices. Stimulate MA innovation partnerships in European and national AKIS.
Policy makers	Get evidence for effective CSF practices for mitigation and adaptation. Benefit from a wide range of recommendations for effective CS-AS and CS-ASPs, networking, demos, and rewarding mechanisms.

Table 4 Target groups and key messages

5 Dissemination and exploitation strategy

Dissemination and exploitation efforts start when first outputs are produced. These activities serve several crucial purposes aimed at maximizing the impact of the project's results:

- **Promoting accessibility:** The primary goal is to ensure that the outputs and findings of the project are easily accessible to those who can benefit from them. This involves making the information available through various channels and formats to reach a wide audience and foster broader adoption
- **Identifying Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and their target audiences:** KERs are the pivotal project outputs that have the potential to create the most significant impact. Identifying these KERs is essential for focusing resources and efforts on areas where they can be leveraged effectively
- **Educating End Users:** It is important to educate the identified end users of the KERs, enabling them to effectively utilize the outputs and make practical use of the project results.

Target group	Interest / Need	Project outputs	Means of dissemination and exploitation
Agricultural advisors and advisory services	<p>Interested in acquiring additional knowledge about CSF practices and advisory approaches to boost their capacity in assisting farmers and enhancing the sustainability of their farming businesses within the realm of climate-smart agriculture.</p> <p>Furthermore, eager to enhance the role of advisors in both national and regional CS-AKIS while aligning with the objectives of the CAP.</p>	<p>Innovative training modules, methods and tools to support farmers in adopting climate smart farming practices</p> <p>CSA TTT module</p> <p>Network of trained CSCs</p> <p>Analysis of the role of the advisors in the ecosystem</p> <p>Synthesis report of key lessons from training interventions</p> <p>Portfolio and classification of CSF MIPs</p> <p>Innovation process support tools for CSA CoDIEs</p>	<p><u>Tools:</u> Knowledge repository Online training platform Practice abstracts Press release articles</p> <p><u>Channels:</u> Trainings CoP/P2P learning events National CS-AKIS and EU networks of project partner organisations CFD project Umbrella organizations like EUFRAS, IALB & SEASN Project website Project social media networks External newsletter International conferences organised by the project EIP Agri Service Point and CAP Networks i2connect's AS database</p>
Farmers	Eager to receive customized, hands-on guidance for implementing CSF practices and exploring potential rewarding mechanisms.	<p>EIP-AGRI Practice Abstracts</p> <p>High quality videos on the FarmDemo YouTube channel</p> <p>Network of trained advisors (CSCs and CSAs)</p>	<p><u>Tools:</u> CSA Knowledge repository Print material: posters, flyers Video materials</p> <p><u>Channels:</u> Advisors Agricultural fairs Social media (especially Facebook)</p>

Target group	Interest / Need	Project outputs	Means of dissemination and exploitation
			<p>Farmers' associations</p> <p>Agricultural magazines, journals and portals</p> <p>TV/radio</p> <p>EIP Agri Service Point and CAP Networks</p> <p>Demonstrations</p> <p>CFD project</p>
Research and education	<p>Eager to engage in collaborative multi-actor partnerships that expedite the development of impactful CSF practices.</p> <p>Additionally, interested in educating students about the pivotal role of CSAs in the journey toward achieving climate-neutral farming.</p>	<p>Knowledge repository</p> <p>TTT module</p> <p>Synthesis report of key lessons from training interventions</p> <p>Portfolio and classification of CSF MIPs</p> <p>Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning (ME&L) framework, methods and tools to provide formative evaluation of CSA network objectives and activities</p>	<p><u>Tools:</u></p> <p>Knowledge repository</p> <p>Scientific posters</p> <p>Open science publications</p> <p><u>Channels:</u></p> <p>Project website and social media (especially LinkedIn)</p> <p>International conferences organised by the project</p> <p>Participation to topic-related conferences</p> <p>Scientific journals</p>
EIP Agri Service Point and CAP Networks	<p>Interested in enhancing recognition and bolstering support from regional and national CS-AKIS to advance the delivery of more effective Advisory Services with a focus on CSF practices.</p> <p>Keen to foster collaborative multi-actor innovation partnerships both at the European and national levels within the AKIS.</p>	<p>Innovative governance approaches for CS-AKIS</p> <p>Sustainability strategy for the network across MS & ACs</p>	<p><u>Tools:</u></p> <p>Practice abstracts</p> <p><u>Channels:</u></p> <p>Project website</p> <p>Project social media networks</p> <p>national and transnational AKIS workshops</p> <p>International conferences organised by the project</p>
Policy makers	<p>Interested in receiving concrete results and evidence-backed recommendations that illuminate the impact pathways.</p> <p>Enthusiastic about actively participating in events, demonstrations, networking opportunities, and engaging in meaningful face-to-face dialogues.</p>	<p>Innovative governance approaches for CS-AKIS</p> <p>CS-AKIS descriptions at regional/national level in partner countries</p> <p>Policy recommendations sustainability strategy for the network across MS & ACs</p>	<p><u>Tools:</u></p> <p>Policy briefs</p> <p>Report on Good CS-AKIS governance practices</p> <p><u>Channels:</u></p> <p>Project website</p> <p>Bilateral meetings</p> <p>TV/radio</p> <p>International Conferences organised by the project</p>

Table 5 Target groups, relevant results and means of dissemination

While dissemination entails making results accessible to the target audience, exploitation goes a step further by indicating the active utilization of these results, including in subsequent research endeavours. WP8 will collaborate closely with other WPs to pinpoint optimal strategies for leveraging outputs, aiming to enhance the impact of the CSA project.

6 DEC tools and channels

The DEC strategy endeavours to engage a substantial number of actors and stakeholders at project and national levels. Consequently, all DEC materials will be thoughtfully crafted to exert a far-reaching influence across all 27 countries. This chapter is dedicated to introducing tools specifically devised to facilitate effective Dissemination and Communication (D&C) at both the national and EU levels. These tools are poised to provide valuable support to all WPs in their quest to realize the envisioned outcomes.

6.1 CSA logo

The ClimateSmartAdvisors logotype embodies the project's multi-actor approach, emphasizing collaboration among various stakeholders to empower advisors and foster a climate-smart advisory community. Achieving this representation involves symbolic design elements, such as the integration of multiple vibrant lines arranged in close proximity, forming a circular shape. The deliberate choice of colours is a key aspect of the design—shades of blue are employed to convey the rational and thoughtful nature of advisors, while the yellow-green hue symbolizes the sun, illustrating its significance as a primary energy source as well as nature, land and sustainability. These thoughtful design elements collectively embody the project's core values and objectives, making the logotype a powerful visual representation of its mission.

Figure 1 Project logotype

Every dissemination material will prominently display the project logo, accompanied by the EU emblem and a clear statement indicating the project's funding from the Horizon Europe program.

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101084179.

Figure 2 EU emblem

6.1.1 Black, white and grayscale

Different platforms, backgrounds, and media have varying colour capabilities. Having a range of logo versions (full colour, black, white, and grayscale) ensures the logo looks great and is recognizable in any situation.

- **Black Logo:** A monochromatic black version of the logotype and the grayscale are useful for scenarios where colour printing may be limited, expensive, or unnecessary. Printing in black and white is common for documents, invoices, or faxing. Furthermore, when placed on colourful backgrounds with light tones, the black logotype is necessary, as the full-colour logo is not suitable, and the white logo is not visible.
- **White Logo (Reverse):** The white version is used on dark or coloured backgrounds where the full-colour logo may not stand out effectively. It ensures the logo remains visible and maintains a professional look.

Figure 3 Project logotypes in monochrome and grayscale

6.2 Corporate colours

In the Climate Smart Advisors colour palette, we embrace multiple colours deeply rooted in nature, reflecting the lushness of vegetation, the warmth of sunlight, and the lightness of the sky. Moreover, blue symbolizes trust, reliability, wisdom, and knowledge—qualities highly desirable in an advisor, who plays a central role in the CSA project. Additionally, the vibrant

nuances of yellow-green symbolize freshness, growth, harmony, balance, eco-friendliness, and sustainability, clearly illustrating the project's ambition toward sustainable agriculture.

The precise colour system codes are visually depicted in the figure below.

Figure 4 Project colour scheme

6.3 Document templates and the first wave of communication material

Appropriate referencing and templates are to be utilized whenever representing CSA in written materials, online platforms, meetings, external conferences, workshops, and similar contexts. Figures 5, 6, 7, 8 present templates and communication material produced during the first six months of the project's implementation.

Title of the document

Subtitle

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Figure 5 Project documents

CLIMATE SMART ADVISORS

Towards a climate smart EU advisory community

- 73 Advisory Service Providers
- 57 Advisory Service Providers
- 260 Communities of Practice
- 140 Climate Smart Coaches
- 1360 Climate Smart Advisors
- 27 National CS-AKIS Networks
- 12 Thematic Areas
- 8-10 Co-Design Innovation Experiments

Agricultural Sectors
Animal husbandry
Mixed farming systems Arable crops
Horticulture
Other

Advisory Service providers
Public
Private
NGO & Non-profit

✉ climatesmartadvisors@ilvo.vlaanderen.be ✕ CSAdvisors_EU 📘 ClimateSmartAdvisors

12 CLIMATE SMART ADVISORS' THEMATIC AREAS

CLIMATE SMART ADVISORS

Focus
Strengthening the advisors' capacity in providing climate-smart advice

Activities

- Dedicated training for 140 advisors to become Climate Smart Coaches.
- Setting up 260 advisory Communities of Practice, led by the Climate Smart Coaches, to create a network of 1360 Climate Smart Advisors.
- Supporting the network through EU-level knowledge exchange on 12 thematic areas, and the development of an online knowledge repository.

Focus
Boosting the advisors' role in the transition towards climate-smart farming

Activities

- Connecting to local and EU (multi-actor innovation) projects, initiatives, AKIS actors, and policy makers to address joint needs, challenges and lessons learned.
- Setting-up of Co-Design Innovation Experiments to learn how to strengthen the advisors' role in innovation processes.

QR code:

✉ climatesmartadvisors@ilvo.vlaanderen.be ✕ CSAdvisors_EU 📘 ClimateSmartAdvisors

Provided by the European Union
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Figure 6 General project flyer

Figure 7 Poster

Figure 8 Roll up

6.4 Project website and platform

The project website will be developed using a participatory design approach, incorporating input from a diverse array of partners who will use the website for various purposes. The website functions as a central hub for vital project information, disseminates updates and results, offers insights into project events and activities, and serves as a repository for all the outcomes generated throughout the project, including but not limited to:

- TTT training module (WP2);
- Online training platform containing all training modules and materials developed under WP2 and WP5;
- Subset of the CSA database (WP1);
- Knowledge repository (WP5);
- Practice abstracts (WP8).

To ensure accessibility and inclusivity, the website will be accessible in both English and the local languages of the respective project partners. The development of the website falls under Deliverable 8.6, which is due in Month 10.

To ensure the broadest possible dissemination within the agricultural community and capitalize on synergies with other projects, particularly our sister projects, the knowledge

repository and online training module will contribute to the project platform integrated into the Climate Farm Demo platform. Additionally, they will be linked to the EUFarmBook platform.

6.4.1 General information and KPIs

General information	
Responsible	BIOS
Contribution	WPLs, all partners
Target audience	Advisors, researchers/academia, farmers, policy makers, project partners
Communicated via	Partners' channels, project social media channels, project newsletters, press, externally (CFD channels, EU CAP network)
KPIs	
Number of visitors	60000
Number of page views	100000

Table 6 Project website and the platform KPIs

6.5 Social media channels

Social media is pivotal for widespread communication, engagement, and information dissemination in today's interconnected world. In the first stage of implementation, the CSA will focus most of its efforts on already tested platforms:

- X (Twitter)
- LinkedIn
- YouTube

In the later stages of the project, CSA will share its results on two additional networks:

- Facebook (content will be also shared in national languages)
- Instagram (content will be shared in English)

Additional insights into the selection rationale for these platforms, the intended audience on social media, content creation, and monitoring can be explored in Chapter 5 of this document, which focuses on the devised social media strategy for CSA.

In addition to the official CSA channels, partners will utilize their profiles on various social media platforms to disseminate pertinent project information. This approach has the potential to greatly expand the reach of the CSA project, engaging a significant number of agricultural stakeholders across Europe. The CSA project consortium, comprising 65 partners throughout Europe, forms a noteworthy network. The partners collectively manage almost 200 corporate social media channels. As a part of the National DEC plans, these channels will be strategically connected to the project's official social media channels, enhancing the impact of communication efforts. Given the widespread social media presence of the majority of partners, it is anticipated that they will both share content from the official CSA pages and generate their own content related to the project.

General information	
Responsible	BIOS
Contribution	WPLs, all partners
Target audience	Advisors, researchers/academia, farmers, policy makers
Communicated via	Project website, partners' channels, project newsletters, press, externally (CFD channels, other projects)

KPIs	
Number of platforms used	5
Number of posts across all platforms	2500
Number of people reached	100 000

Table 7 Project social media channel and KPIs

6.6 Project newsletter

Climate Smart Advisors WP8 is set to generate and circulate newsletters that will deliver up-to-date information regarding advancements, undertakings, and accessible outcomes of the project to stakeholders and wider audiences involved in climate mitigation and agriculture throughout Europe. This encompasses the agriculture advisor community, farming community, research and academia, agro-businesses, policymakers, and civil society. The newsletters will be bifurcated into two categories: internal newsletters tailored for Consortium members and external newsletters tailored for the audience beyond the project's confines, that will be created and distributed jointly with ClimateFarmDemo sister project, in order to reach even broader audience.

The main purpose of the external CSA newsletter is to:

- Foster and maintain relationships with relevant stakeholders;
- Keep the audience informed about important updates, project progress, and project activities, including upcoming events and capacity building and knowledge exchange opportunities;
- Disseminate project results;
- Announce important milestones, achievements, and updates within the project;
- Promote different events within the project;
- Share information that not necessarily arises from the CSA project, but is relevant for the advisory and agriculture ecosystems;
- Increase social media followers, engagement and impressions;
- Increase website traffic, visibility, and improve Search Engine Optimization (SEO).

The main purpose of the internal CSA newsletter is to:

- Facilitate effective communication and information-sharing among the project partners, and provide them with concise information about the overall progress of project implementation;
- Update all stakeholders directly involved in the project about the latest developments, progress, outcomes and results;
- Track the project's progress by highlighting milestones, achievements, and challenges, and identifying areas that need attention;
- Provide project partners with a summarised list of upcoming activities, and set a reminder;
- Provide project partners with updates on new tools and materials developed under the Project;
- Encourage further dissemination of project results and promotion of project activities by all partners.

6.6.1 General information

The BioSense Institute manages newsletters using the Mailchimp service, with contributions primarily from MT members and occasionally other project partners. The newsletters are exclusively in English. Subsequently, each National Coordinator has the flexibility to translate the content into their local language and distribute it through their respective

channels, such as the organizational website or mailing list. The project website has a built-in subscription form that enables the audience to sign up for the newsletter. We have a total of 56 newsletters, and their release schedule follows a content-first approach. This approach enables WP8 members to modify the publication frequency based on project progress and planned activities, with a primary focus on quarterly publishing.

The project has also taken into account 50 partner newsletters across 27 countries, collectively reaching a minimum of 120,000 recipients. These partner newsletters are planned to reference the project at least biannually, ensuring a consistent presence and engagement within the broader network.

General information	
Responsible	WP8, BIOS
Contribution	WPLs, all partners
Target audience	External: Advisors, researchers/academia, farmers, policy makers, project partners Internal: project partners
Communicated via	Project website, project social media channels
KPIs	
Number of publications	Min 56
Number of subscribers	External: 3000 Internal: 150
Number of email opening	External: 10 000 Internal: 1 000
Number of clicks	External: 6 000 Internal: 2 000

Table 8 Project newsletter and KPIs

6.6.2 Newsletter content

The external newsletters convey details about project activities that hold significance for both project stakeholders and a broader audience. These newsletters encompass updates on project outcomes, training resources, notifications regarding project events, virtual and physical training sessions, workshops, webinars, and pertinent information. Each edition of the newsletter will mirror the overarching advancement of the project, and every MT member will be encouraged to provide pertinent information and share attained results. These details will be primarily mapped during biannual meetings between WP8 and other WPs, but also during monthly WP8 meetings with the Project Coordinator. The internal newsletter will be focused on supporting internal communication, presenting an overview of the achieved results, and reminding the partners about upcoming activities. Furthermore, it will strengthen the project's progress track, and summarise and link all tools and materials developed that can be helpful for all partners in their day-to-day activities in one place. All WP leaders will be invited to contribute to the content creation and use the opportunity of issuing the internal newsletter to inform the consortium about the progress made under all WPs.

While the newsletters provide a broader channel of information dissemination, the network management unit (NMU) focuses specifically on maintaining a direct line of communication with National Coordinators (NCs). This tailored approach ensures that NCs are well-informed, engaged, and supported in their roles as key project representatives at the national level, while at the same time, WP8 stays informed about the activities that are taking place in each country and ensures external newsletter also encompasses the news coming from the national networks/CoP activities.

6.7 Press releases

A Press Kit will be designed and produced to connect with specialized journalists on both national and European levels, as well as engage the most pertinent media outlets. This initiative aims to enhance the Climate Smart Advisors communication endeavours, effectively reaching demographics that might not be covered by other communication and dissemination strategies. Press releases will be a pivotal element in broadening the project's outreach. The project plans to develop approximately 20 press releases in English. Subsequently, these articles will be translated by project partners into local languages and distributed through regional and national media platforms. Moreover, there are 15 TV and radio appearances expected.

General information	
Responsible	WP8; BIOS and National Coordinators
Target audience	Media, advisors, farmers, general audience
Communicated via	Project website, partners' websites, relevant portals, magazines, journals, newspapers, TV and radio
KPIs	
Number of press kits	20
Number of media outlets (excluding radio and TV)	50
Number of TV/radio appearances	15

Table 9 Press releases and KPIs

6.8 Practice abstracts

The innovative knowledge and tools generated by this project will be shared widely with practitioners in form of Practice Abstracts, through the project website and social media, but also through the EU CAP Network website <https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/>. Specifically, user-friendly materials will be crafted, condensing this knowledge into "practice abstracts" in the standardized EIP format. All 27 National Coordinators will play a vital role by creating a minimum of 10 practice abstracts each.

A total target number of 300 Practice Abstracts on the toolkits is foreseen for the project. Practice abstracts will be reported in three batches, each presenting 100 pieces: D8.7 EIP practice abstracts – batch 1, delivered in M36; D8.8 EIP practice abstracts – batch 2, submitted in M60; and D8.9 EIP practice abstracts – batch 3, submitted in M84.

General information	
Responsible	WP8; BIOS and National Coordinators
Target audience	Advisors, farmers, policy makers
Communicated via	Project website, social media, newsletter, EU CAP Network
KPIs	
Number of publications	300
Number of people reached	10000

Table 10 Practice abstracts and KPIs

6.9 Multimedia

Climate Smart Advisors will leverage the already established YouTube channel, FarmDemo, to ensure its successful implementation. Within the scope of the CSA project, we are

committed to creating a minimum of 100 high-quality technical and tutorial videos, collaboratively produced by BIOS and all partners. These videos will serve as valuable resources for explaining complex concepts, promoting effective Climate-Smart Farming (CSF) practices and advisory methods, fostering knowledge sharing among advisors, farmers, and other stakeholders.

In addition to technical content, these videos will feature testimonials from CS advisors and farmers, offering an intimate glimpse into the tangible results of the project. All of these meticulously crafted videos will find their home on the FarmDemo channel and will be actively promoted across the project's social media channels. Moreover, selected videos will be featured in both external and internal newsletters, amplifying their reach and impact.

General information	
Responsible	WP8, BIOS
Contributions	WPLs, NCs
Target audience	Advisors, farmers, EU policy makers;
Communicated via	YouTube, project website, newsletter, social media
KPIs	
Number of videos produces	100
Total number of views	30000

Table 11 Video content and KPIs

6.10 CSA events

ClimateSmartAdvisors will organise a minimum of two (2) International Conferences, strategically designed to convene coordinators and key partners from related (sister) projects. These conferences will feature tailor-made workshops with the express purpose of fostering interconnections among the aforementioned projects. Beyond these gatherings orchestrated by CSA, the project is set to take part in a minimum of twenty (20) prominent conferences focused on Climate, Advisory and Extension, or Research and Innovation (R&I).

Over the course of the project's scope, ClimateSmartAdvisors will organise eight (8) General Assembly (GA) meetings that will engage representatives of all partnering organisation. Additionally, an extensive count of one hundred (100) public events is anticipated, which will unfold either at Climate Farm Demo (CFD) Partner Demonstration Farms (PDFs) or at experimental stations. In addition, CSCs are expected to deliver a series of training events aligned with each CoP wave. Furthermore, they will deliver seminars and workshops for wider advisory community and (future) climate advisors. These events are geared towards engaging CS advisors, Climate Smart Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (CS-AKIS) stakeholders, researchers, and farmers alike.

International Conferences	
Responsible	WP8, ILVO, WP7
Contributions	IDELE, ACTA (co-organisation with CFD), BIOS, WP leads, WP7
Target audience	Advisors, farmers, relevant EU projects representatives, EU policy makers;
Communicated via	Dedicated communication campaign that includes: CSA and CFD project websites, newsletters, social media channels, EU CAP Network website and newsletter, targeted mailing (for policy makers and relevant projects) workshops, bilateral meetings
KPIs	
Number of conferences	2

Total number of participants	500
Total number of people reached through dedicated communication campaign	10000
Trainings by CSCs for wider advisory community	
Responsible	WP2, SRUC, SZE
Contributions	FueAk, TEAG, IDELE, SRUC, CSCs
Target audience	Advisors and future advisors
Communicated via	National communication channels – respective partners networks and channels, local/national media
KPIs	
Number of trainings	140
Total number of participants	2800
External events (agricultural fairs and scientific or technical conferences)	
Responsible	WP7
Contributions	All WP Leaders
Target audience	Researchers/academia, advisors, farmers, EU policymakers, relevant EU projects representatives, general audience, media
Communicated via	Dedicated communication campaign that includes: CSA and CFD project websites, newsletters, social media channels, EU CAP Network website and newsletter, targeted mailing (for policy makers and relevant projects) workshops, bilateral meetings
KPIs	
Number of agricultural fairs	97
Number of scientific or technical conferences	28
Number of visitors (agriculture professionals)	>2,000,000
Number of visitors (researchers)	>13,000
Potential number of people reached through dedicated communication campaign	>2,013,000

Table 12 Project public events and KPIs

6.11 Open access publications

Employing open science formats for publications serves as highly effective channel for disseminating CSA outputs to academic and research communities. Scientific publications play a crucial role in generating knowledge impact and facilitating the utilization of project findings. In terms of content, pivotal results and outputs derived from the CSA will be shared through the abstract submitted to relevant conferences and topic-related journals.

General information	
Responsible	Scientists involved in CSA activities on both EU and national level
Target audience	Primary: the scientific community and academia Secondary: policymakers on EU and national levels, CS advisors
Communicated via	Conferences, magazines and journals; summaries disseminated through the project website, project newsletter and social media channels
KPIs	
Number of publications	20
Number of conferences	20

Table 13 Publications and KPIs

6.12 Policy briefs

As a result of the project's findings, there will be produced a minimum of five policy briefs addressing various topics related to climate-smart practices and advisory methods. These topics include innovation brokering, farmer adoption, CSAKIS, CS-Advisory, and international collaboration. The primary goal of these policy briefs is to furnish policymakers with valuable insights from the advisory community and offer policy recommendations aimed at enhancing policy design and evaluation. These recommendations will be grounded in real-world data derived from the CSA project results. This initiative will serve as a crucial foundation for fostering meaningful dialogues with policymakers at both the national (ministries) and EU (EC) levels.

General information	
Responsible	WP7, CONSULAI
Contributions	WP6, EUFRAS, NCs
Target audience	EU policy makers; national policy makers
Communicated via	Workshops, bilateral meetings, targeted mailing, project website and newsletters
KPIs	
Number of policy briefs	5
Number of actors reached	60

Table 14 Policy briefs and KPIs

7 Dissemination and exploitation of project results: success criteria

This chapter summarizes the main project results and provides pathways and success criteria for the outreach.

Result	Metrics	Target audience	Means of communication
Toolkit on advisory methods and training approaches	50 x 27 languages	Advisors	Project website, knowledge repository, project newsletter and social media, partners' networks and channels, EU CAP network
Means of Dissemination and Exploitation	Metrics	KPI (related to communication)	KPI (related to dissemination)
Trainings, physical and online workshops, conferences, CoP training/P2P learning events	>2500 training sessions 2 international conferences 2080 CoP training/P2P learning events	10000 advisors reached	5000 advisors involved

Result	Metrics	Target audience	Means of communication
CSA TTT module	4 workshops 140 CSCs trained	Advisors (CSCs)	Project website, knowledge repository, project newsletter and social media, partners' networks and channels, EU CAP network
Means of Dissemination and Exploitation	Metrics	KPI (related to communication)	KPI (related to dissemination)
Trainings, public events and physical or online workshops, conferences	1,500 advisors upskilled (TTT & CoPs) 250 training seminars for advisors 150 training workshops for future advisors	10000 advisors reached	1500 advisors involved

Result	Metrics	Target audience	Means of communication
Policy briefs	5	Policy makers on EU level (EC) Policy makers on national level (ministries)	Project website, knowledge repository, project newsletter and social media, partners' networks and channels, EU CAP network
Means of Dissemination and Exploitation	Metrics	KPI (related to communication)	KPI (related to dissemination)
Bilateral meetings, workshops, conferences, targeted mails	Tba in the D8.2	Tba in the D8.2	60 individuals/entities engaged in dissemination activities

Result	Metrics	Target audience	Means of communication
Practice abstracts	300	Policy makers on EU level (EC) Policy makers on national level (ministries)	Project website, knowledge repository, project newsletter and social media, partners' networks and channels, EU CAP network website and newsletters
Means of Dissemination and Exploitation	Metrics	KPI (related to communication)	KPI (related to dissemination)
Bilateral meetings, workshops, conferences, targeted mails	Tba in the D8.2	Tba in the D8.2	60 individuals/entities engaged in dissemination activities

Result	Metrics	Target audience	Means of communication
Videos	100	Advisors, farmers	Youtube channel, project website, social media and newsletter
Means of Dissemination and Exploitation	Metrics	KPI (related to communication)	KPI (related to dissemination)
n/a	n/a	15000 views	n/a

Result	Metrics	Target audience	Means of communication
Knowledge repository	1	Advisors, farmers, researchers, policy makers	project website, social media and newsletter, EU CAP Network website and newsletter, CFD website, FarmBook
Means of Dissemination and Exploitation	Metrics	KPI (related to communication)	KPI (related to dissemination)
Trainings, conferences, workshops	>2500 trainings, >100 public events and workshops, 2 conferences internally organised, 20 participation in conferences	300 000 people reached	13 000 people engaged (10000 advisors, 1500 farmers, 1500 through conferences)

Table 15 Main results and relevant KPIs

8 Social media strategy

Throughout the previous decade, social media platforms have significantly contributed to raising awareness of different projects, increasing their visibility, sharing information, and interacting with pertinent communities, all directed at enhancing the promotion of project events, sharing exemplary practices within the specific sector, and advancing overarching project objectives. This section delineates the approach that CSA will adopt to accomplish these objectives.

8.1 Social media objectives

For the social media strategy to be impactful, it's imperative to meticulously formulate objectives that are both ambitious and attainable. The ensuing objectives are deemed vital in their contribution to the overarching project outcomes.

- Draw attention to the project and its scope at EU, national, and local levels;
- Drive traffic to the CSA platform;
- Encourage people to subscribe to the project newsletter;
- Boost the number of views on CSA videos;
- Boost the visibility of advisor's activities;
- Promote the best practices to stimulate the exchange of knowledge among farming actors across Europe;
- Share project results and outputs
- Disseminate educational content and resources related to the project's focus areas to enhance knowledge sharing.

Focusing on more specific objectives, it's crucial for the strategy to excel in establishing effective communication and fostering engagement with pertinent stakeholders across the project's duration. Therefore, the aim is to:

- identify and amplify target audiences;
- tailor key messages for the different audiences on each social media platform;
- ensure creation and publishing of relevant, impactful and visually appealing content;
- create a growth hacking strategy and specify key performance indicators (KPIs);
- promote and encourage attendance at project-related events, workshops, and conferences;
- utilize relevant hashtags and participate in trending conversations to increase the project's visibility;
- monitor and evaluate the process to recognise the most fruitful efforts.

Meeting these objectives will allow for the overall CSA potential to be maximised.

8.2 Social media platforms

CSA is actively engaging with stakeholders and users through various primary channels, including social media platforms such as LinkedIn, X (Twitter), and YouTube. In the upcoming phase (Y2), the project plans to expand its network to include users on Instagram and Facebook. It's worth noting that platform popularity varies across regions and nations; however, the ones mentioned have historically demonstrated efficacy within this context. CSA's social media accounts will be administered in English, given its status as a lingua franca. The only exception will be the management of the Facebook page. This platform will primarily target the farming community, which is known to use Facebook more frequently than other social media networks. However, since farmers primarily use this platform in their

native language, CSA will leverage it to disseminate region-specific information and announcements.

You can locate all of the project's social media channels conveniently listed in Table 18 within the Annexes section of this document.

8.2.1 X (Twitter)

The @CSAdvisors_EU X (Twitter) account has been established to disseminate concise yet informative content. Given that the project is currently in its initial phases as of this deliverable submission, it's anticipated that both the follower count and engagement will progressively experience a more significant upswing over time.

The account will serve as a platform for sharing project developments, outcomes, alongside subjects and concepts aligned with the core essence and thematic domains of CSA. Furthermore, it's essential to consistently:

- check the homepage and potentially retweet content related to CSA from project partners and other relevant organizations and/or projects;
- focus on delivering valuable, high-quality, and relevant content that resonates with the audience;
- respond promptly to comments, mentions, and direct messages to foster interaction and build relationships;
- reply promptly to comments and mentions;
- utilize relevant and trending hashtags to increase the visibility of tweets;
- stay updated with the latest news and trends relevant for the project and its thematic areas;
- analyse project's X (Twitter) analytics to understand what's working and adjust the strategy accordingly;
- tag project partners in relevant posts in order to increase engagement;
- check for new followers and follow back if appropriate.

Figure 9 X Page

8.2.2 LinkedIn

The project leverages a LinkedIn account (www.linkedin.com/company/climatesmartadvisors/) to broaden its reach to a wider range of target audiences. It achieves this by mirroring the latest pertinent updates from the CSA website, disseminating industry news, highlighting networking prospects for both advisors and farmers, and more.

To ensure proper communication and maximum effectiveness, it is necessary to regularly:

- disseminate relevant and valuable content regularly;
- engage with connections and followers by responding to comments and messages promptly, and fostering discussions;
- monitor the performance of the posts and page by using LinkedIn Analytics;
- review new followers and follow them back if it's relevant or appropriate;
- connect with project partners, as well as relevant professionals and thought leaders within the field;
- use relevant and trending hashtags in the posts to increase discoverability and engagement;
- share informative and educational content that provides value to the target audiences;
- share the CSA LinkedIn page URL on the website, in email signatures, and on other social media platforms to encourage cross-platform growth.

Figure 10 LinkedIn Page

8.2.3 YouTube

Around one hundred (100) high quality videos created by the project will be uploaded to the FarmDemo channel on YouTube, used by the RUR-11 projects PLAID, AgriDemo F2F, NEFERTITI and Climate Farm Demo. This means an additional boost for the potential of CSA videos since the channel is already well-established, with around 1,740 subscribers. Therefore, new video material is likely to gain much more attention than it would had there been a separate, new channel launched.

The CSA videos will be shared to other social media platforms like Twitter and LinkedIn, as they serve as an effective means to draw in a larger viewership. These videos will take different forms (e.g. lecture-style tutorials, testimonials, etc.), intended to enhance the impact in conveying key findings. Whenever feasible, the content will be created in local languages, with subtitles provided in select partner languages. Furthermore, to expedite the distribution of these videos, CSA partners are encouraged to promote them on their national websites and social media profiles.

Figure 11 FarmDemo YouTube channel

8.2.4 Facebook

A project Facebook page will kick off in the Y2 of project implementation. As the internal research conducted in sister project CFD showcased, the Facebook is the main social media channel used by farmers across the EU. CSA will invest its effort in Facebook mainly for sharing knowledge and activities undertaken on national level. More specifically, Facebook will serve for:

- sharing information about events and opportunities on national level;
- disseminating produced knowledge, findings and best practices;
- connecting directly with project partners, CS advisors and CS farmers.

8.2.5 Instagram

Instagram will be launched when the first set of videos is ready. As a visually-oriented social media platform, Instagram will serve as an ideal space for sharing concise video clips extracted from YouTube content, thus appealing to a younger audience of advisors and students. Instagram will have several objectives, including but not limited to:

- further dissemination of video content;
- dissemination of project results in a visually appealing way;
- attracting younger advisers and students.

8.3 Target audience on social media and key messages

One of the goals of the CSA project is to reach several different kinds of target audiences via social media. The following table shows the main purpose of posts for each group and key messages.

Agricultural Advisors and Advisory Services	
Purpose/Impact	To enhance advisors' capacity to support farmers; to strengthen advisors' key role in regional and national CS-AKIS; to expand the network through dissemination channels; to support advisors in co-creating new and innovative solutions, and business models; to boost advisors' capability in navigating the transition towards CSF approaches.

Key message(s)	Advisors play a pivotal role in offering enhanced support, valuable advice, and empowering guidance to farmers. They are nurtured and encouraged to take on the important role of catalysts for change and innovation within the CSF's multi-level transitions. Advisors are granted the valuable opportunity to become part of the CoP network, enabling them to exchange knowledge, actively engage in CoDIES activities, and assume the crucial role of driving change and innovation within the CSF's multi-level transitions.
Farmers	
Purpose/Impact	To experience a positive impact through various public and/or private incentives, resulting in a substantial adoption of adaptation and mitigation measures, notably carbon sequestration; to contribute to the enhancement of farm income and the elevation of farmers' status within the value chain through incentive-based mechanisms; to increase further awareness and active participation in the sustainable transitions towards CSF practices.
Key message(s)	Farmers receive valuable support in the form of personalized advice and cutting-edge tools, empowering them to make a meaningful reduction in their climate footprint. Through a combination of public and/or private incentives, farmers experience a substantial adoption of adaptation and mitigation measures, with a particular emphasis on carbon sequestration. These efforts are further reinforced by incentives that recognize and reward their commitment to sustainable practices, ensuring the economic viability of their agricultural endeavours. Farmers are effectively lowering GHG while simultaneously bolstering carbon sequestration through the implementation of cost-effective adaptation and mitigation measures.
Research And Education	
Purpose/Impact	To experience a positive impact through various public and/or private incentives, resulting in a substantial adoption of adaptation and mitigation measures, notably carbon sequestration; to contribute to the enhancement of farm income and the elevation of farmers' status within the value chain through incentive-based mechanisms; to increase further awareness and active participation in the sustainable transitions towards CSF practices.
Key message(s)	Farmers receive valuable support in the form of personalized advice and cutting-edge tools, empowering them to make a meaningful reduction in their climate footprint. Through a combination of public and/or private incentives, farmers experience a substantial adoption of adaptation and mitigation measures, with a particular emphasis on carbon sequestration. These efforts are further reinforced by incentives that recognize and reward their commitment to sustainable practices, ensuring the economic viability of their agricultural endeavours. Farmers are effectively lowering GHG while simultaneously bolstering carbon sequestration through the implementation of cost-effective adaptation and mitigation measures.
Policy makers	
Purpose/Impact	To accelerate advisors and farmers engagement with CSF and sustainable transition through designing and promoting new policy incentives; to fund innovative CSF projects to reach EU Climate strategy objectives; to improve decision making by taking advantage of white spot analysis.
Key message(s)	Policy makers should prioritize the acquisition of evidence supporting the effectiveness of Climate-Smart Farming (CSF) practices for both mitigation and adaptation. They can take advantage of a diverse array of recommendations encompassing effective Climate-Smart Agriculture (CS-AS) and Climate-Smart Agri-Service Providers (CS-ASPs), as well as guidance on networking, demonstrations, and incentive mechanisms.

Table 16 Social media audience and key messages

8.4 Content strategy

8.4.1 Defining content

The content will be thoughtfully tailored to align with the specific requirements of the farming community, which constitutes the project's primary audience, while considering their countries and sectors. This includes:

- easy-to-read text posts;
- pictures, infographics, illustrations, etc. with relevant content;
- videos.

Any member of the CSA consortium can share information to post on social media. If they have information about events, papers/articles or other materials that can be included in the content calendar, they should email dajana@vujaklija@biosense.rs or isidora.colic@biosense.rs.

In addition, any member of the consortium is encouraged to share social media posts on their organisation's channels, ensuring that CSA is tagged and appropriate hashtags are used. It's important to underscore that some content may be of a confidential or sensitive nature, and this aspect should be handled with utmost care to prevent any inadvertent surprises or discomfort.

8.4.2 Growth hacking approach

Aiming to expand the CSA social media following, the growth hacking approach will be employed since it entails marketing and promotional techniques focused on efficient and rapid growth to achieve long-term end-user sustainability. As a result, the content will be carefully prepared, and the project will gain the status of a reliable and educational knowledge reservoir. In the quest to maximize the reach of this valuable content, all CSA partners are strongly encouraged to actively promote it within their professional networks. This can be achieved by inviting followers, sharing, expressing appreciation through likes, and engaging with thoughtful comments.

The main steps should, therefore, be:

- Content optimization
 - Create and use carefully tailored and shareable content that resonates with the project's target audiences
 - Use compelling headlines, visuals, and multimedia elements to grab attention
 - Test the approach by experimenting with formatting styles, posting content at different times of the day, etc.
- A/B testing
 - Continuously experiment with different post types, timings, and content to identify what works best
 - Use data to refine the social media strategy throughout the project's life span
- Leverage user analytics
 - Analyse the performance by monitoring analytics using tools designed for that
 - Monitor the performance of the platforms in the early stages of the project and set reasonable targets for the rest of the project's lifetime
- Engagement and interaction
 - Respond promptly to comments and messages
 - Engage in conversations with the audience to build relationships
- Network building
 - Continuously expand CSA network by connecting with relevant professionals and influencers
 - Internal communication
 - Assess the analytics at regular team meetings to draw conclusions about which posts are the most well-received and engaging and what changes are necessary to improve the results

8.4.3 Content calendar

A social media calendar will be uploaded in the project's online workspace (MS Teams) to ensure that content on social media is generated in an organised and effective way, as well as to provide a neat overview. That includes a monthly content calendar for the CSA's social media. As the WP8 leader, BIOS will design the calendar, which will contain information such as date, topic, message, platform, post link, statistics, and more.

Based on content relevance to a specific region, designated partners will translate and post the content on their respective social media channels. This does not include certain posts

that cannot be available in advance due to their nature (for instance, live-tweeting from meetings, field visits, etc.).

8.4.4 Practical tips & suggested hashtag list

This sub-chapter offers several practical tips that refer to both the C&D team and CSA partners in general.

- Be consistent, but do not resort to repetitive or irrelevant posts if there is a lack of new content;
- Strive to publish grammatically correct and properly formatted posts;
- Keep the tone and language neutral (neither too professional nor too informal), without sounding too technical;
- Share posts on all of your social media channels, if appropriate;
- Engage with your community by responding to comments and direct messages when possible.

As for #ClimateSmartAdvisors (alternatively #CSA if remaining character number does not allow for the longer version). In addition, the following hashtags should be used when appropriate:

- #ClimateSmartAdvisors
- #CSAdvisors
- #HorizonEU
- #SmartFarming
- #ClimateAdaptation
- #ClimateMitigation
- #ClimateChange
- #ClimateAction
- #ClimateNeutrality
- #EUfunding
- #EuGreenDeal
- #GHG
- #AKIS
- #AgriInnovations
- #Sustainability

Other hashtags can be added if necessary. For example, partners may use hashtags in their own language or in connection with particular events.

- #EUconference
- #Paris
- #Dublin
- etc.

9 DEC Action Plan on Project Level

The biannual DEC Action Plan aims to provide a practical and actionable guide for planning and executing DEC activities. Given its close connection to project activities and outcomes, this action plan will be updated every six months, specifically in November and April. It offers an in-depth insight into the processes crucial for ensuring effective communication, dissemination, and exploitation of project results. Furthermore, it underscores the interdependence of roles and responsibilities required for the successful implementation of DEC activities. The plan specifies the starting point, project event, or output, identifies key stakeholders involved, and assigns responsibilities for generating CDE outputs. In cases where the plan pertains to a project output, it will also outline Key Exploitable Results (KERs), target audiences, tools, channels, and timelines for various planning and execution phases.

The creation of the plan has three phases:

1. Identification of the needs

Bilateral meetings with each WP lead that serve to identify the needs for DEC measures in the following year (with focus on the first 6 months). Firstly, we will identify the activities for the upcoming period and the expected outcomes. Then we will define tools and channels based on the i) outcome/activity, ii) target audience of the specific outcome, and iii) DEC goals. To better understand diversity of cases, please see couple of examples below:

- Example 1: In this scenario, the work package is responsible for organizing training sessions specifically tailored for already engaged participants, without extending invitations to a broader audience. In such cases, the communication tools required may be limited to producing email invitations and training programs.
- Example 2: In the event that the work package arranges training sessions intended for a broader community, our focus shifts towards developing a comprehensive plan solely for promoting this particular activity. During the meeting, we will work together to address the following key questions:
 - Who? (target audience) – advisors;
 - What channels do we want to use? – project website, social media, newsletter, existing networks;
 - What tools do we need to produce in order to attract that specific audience through that specific channel? – article for the website (text and visual), invitation video or static visual for social media, short invitation for the newsletter, pdf invitation for existing networks;
 - Do we need registration? If yes, then we need to develop tailored campaigns for people to take action and register;
 - Who will be responsible for each task? Who will be the point of contact providing WP8 with the necessary information and content?;
 - Definition of the timeline.
- Example 3: WP produces policy recommendations. In this case, the process is similar to the one from Example 2, with the main difference being the selection of appropriate channels. When we have project output, our goal is to make it accessible to specific target groups (dissemination), and we also aim to motivate interested parties to further utilize the output (exploitation). So, the questions would be the following:
 - What policymakers do we want to attract?;
 - How can we achieve this? Through face-to-face interactions? Email communication? Conferences? Workshops? Webinars?;

- What kind of tools do we need? Policy briefs. If we're seeing stakeholders in person, then we might want to print them out. If it's online, we can have a PowerPoint presentation, but we can also have a video;
- Who will be responsible for each task?;
- Definition of the timeline.

2. Discussion during DEC meeting

Following the identification of needs, our DEC meetings provide a platform for discussing priorities, incorporating any missing topics that we deem essential for the comprehensive communication of the project, and more.

3. Creation of the Action DEC plan

Once we've gathered all the inputs, we can formulate the DEC Action Plan. This plan will serve as a valuable tool for streamlining the planning and execution of DEC activities. Moreover, it will serve as the foundation for developing the social media calendar, newsletter plan, and national-level DEC Plans.

10 National DEC Plans

As CSA is focused on actively involving and engaging local stakeholders throughout Europe, the primary emphasis in WP8 lies on national communication and dissemination efforts. NCs are tasked with directing their efforts towards securing the commitment of all relevant national Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) participants. They will make use of appropriate national communication and dissemination channels to achieve this goal.

To effectively carry out these responsibilities, the NCs will receive training and encouragement to leverage various networks. This includes, but is not limited to, national AKIS, CAP Networks, their own or third-party websites, social media platforms, and newsletters. National dissemination, exploitation, and communication (DEC) activities will be an integral part of Task 8.3, with valuable inputs from Task 8.1 and Task 8.2.

There are five main aspects of national communication: (i) promotion of the project, its activities, ambition, opportunities, and benefits for the local community; (ii) engaging advisors; (iii) promotion of the training modules and materials, (iv) promotion of supporting activities and capacity building opportunities; and (v) dissemination and exploitation of project results. In the realm of national communication activities, a pivotal aspect involves discerning the types of initiatives that should be orchestrated. These initiatives serve a dual purpose: firstly, to effectively inform local and national stakeholders about the project, and secondly, to devise activities that will inspire their active participation in the project's endeavours.

Although the overall objectives for each country are similar, every country should design its own unique national strategy or approach tailored to its specific requirements. Given the varying project targets, communication methods, and stakeholder practices across countries, the national DEC strategy or approach may exhibit notable differences. However, to effectively monitor the implementation progress and success of DEC plans on a national scale, we have designed adaptable and user-friendly templates. National coordinators will annually formulate DEC plans aligned with the project activities for that respective year. Similarly to the development of DEC action plans on the EU level, the implementation of DEC plan on a national level will start with identifying the needs arising from planned project activities. This first stage will be facilitated by WP8 (EUFRAS and BIOS), during Annual and/or NMU meetings. After that, NCs will create the plans and upload them to the project's SharePoint. A preview of the draft template for national DEC plans is provided in Figure 12 in Annexes section.

11 Monitoring and Evaluation

11.1 Management of DEC activities

Successful DEC initiatives are built upon strong collaboration, not only within WP8 but also across other WPs and NCs. This collaborative approach amplifies the project's communication and dissemination efforts on both international and national levels. Through careful planning and robust partnerships with task leaders, consortium partners, and all project stakeholders, WP8 is well-positioned to achieve its objectives and make a significant impact on the wider community. This section outlines the tasks within WP8, highlighting their interconnectedness and dependencies with both WP8 and other WPs.

WP 8 - Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication will manage all DEC activities on both a European and national scale. The work package is led by BioSense Institute with the support of the Deputy work package leader – EUFRAS.

The roles of the WP8 leader are the following:

- Plan and coordinate implementation of all DEC activities;
- Manage the news and events on the website;
- Manage project's official social media accounts;
- Manage development, creation and distribution of project newsletters and press releases;
- Report on DEC activities, compiling information received by the partners.

National coordinators will have a crucial role in DEC activities, particularly at the national level, where their responsibilities include:

- Creating annual national DEC plans and reports on DEC activities;
- Producing the DEC material in local language (translate the English version of relevant content);
- Adopting it to local context if needed, and/or developing additional material for the purpose of DEC activities on national level);
- Translating and adapting press releases and distributing them to local and national media;
- Ensuring the project gains satisfying local/national coverage, targets and reaches relevant stakeholders;
- Ensuring all relevant project results are disseminated to relevant national and local stakeholders.

Task 8.1: Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) (M1-M84)

Task Leader: BIOS; Partners: EUFRAS

Deliverable 8.1 is developed under this task, and it presents a first draft version of the overall strategy for internal/external communication. It will be updated every 2 years to reflect all changes, new opportunities, and new synergies. This task will actively oversee and track all DEC activities carried out within the project, fostering seamless linking between WP8 and WP7, and the vital connections with other projects, initiatives, and policymakers (PIPs).

Task 8.2: Dissemination and communication activities at project level (M3-M84)

Leader: BIOS

Following the DEC plan, this task will be responsible for developing all DEC tools and materials as well as managing communication channels such as social media accounts, project newsletters, and press releases. All visual material, including the visual identity of the project, graphic materials, print and digital materials, and multimedia, will also be developed under this task, answering the needs of all other work packages and other WP8 tasks.

Task 8.3: Communication and dissemination at National level (M3-M84)

Leader: EUFRAS; Partners: NCs

This task will ensure effective communication at the national level. Annual DEC plans on a national level will help coordinate and effectively monitor DEC activities in all countries. Besides regular DEC activities designed to reach national and local stakeholders, this task will ensure collaboration with PIPs on a national level, according to the plans developed under WP7.

Task 8.4: Capacity building on ClimateSmartAdvisors results (M10-M84)

Leader: BIOS; Partners: OU, EUFRAS

T8.4 will exploit all training modules and materials developed in WP2 and WP5 to make them available to the European agricultural advisory community and other relevant stakeholders across the EU. Based on TTT modules, this task will fine-tune and prepare online training modules for next generation of CS advisors, accessible through the FarmDemo platform and will be linked to external knowledge repositories such as: Open Research Europe, Horizon Results platform, Horizon Results booster, etc.

11.1.1 List of WP8 Deliverables and Milestones

Deliverable number	Deliverable title	Responsible partner	Type	Dissemination level	Due date (month)
D8.1	Draft dissemination, exploitation & communication Plan at EU & National levels	47 - BIOSENSE	R — Document, report	PU - Public	6
D8.2	Updated dissemination, exploitation & communication Plan at EU & National levels	47 - BIOSENSE	R — Document, report	PU - Public	24
D8.3	Final dissemination, exploitation & WP8 communication Plan at EU & National levels	47 - BIOSENSE	R — Document, report	PU - Public	48
D8.4	Digital and printed dissemination, WP8 exploitation and communication material – first set of materials	47 - BIOSENSE	R — Document, report	PU - Public	36
D8.5	Digital and printed dissemination, WP8 exploitation and communication material – final set of materials	47 - BIOSENSE	R — Document, report	PU - Public	84

Deliverable number	Deliverable title	Responsible partner	Type	Dissemination level	Due date (month)
D8.6	Project website	47 - BIOSENSE	DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	PU - Public	10
D8.7	Practice abstracts - batch 1	47 - BIOSENSE	R — Document, report	PU - Public	36
D8.8	Practice abstracts - batch 2	47 - BIOSENSE	R — Document, report	PU - Public	60
D8.9	Practice abstracts - batch 3	47 - BIOSENSE	R — Document, report	PU - Public	84
D8.10	CSA Online Training Platform	47 - BIOSENSE	DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	PU - Public	84

Table 17 Table of Deliverables and Milestones

11.1.2 Monitoring system

For constant monitoring of DEC activities, and to ensure that all partners understand and align with the project's overarching objectives and DEC goals, various tools will be adopted:

- Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Reporting available to all partners on the project SharePoint;
- WP8 monthly meetings;
- Annual DEC meetings between WP8 and other WPs;
- DEC annually meetings between the WP8 members and NCs;
- Annual plans and reports.

To ensure a strategic and organized approach to DEC activities at the national level, there will be annual national plans established. These plans will serve as a framework for the DEC endeavours and will also incorporate a section that provides a comprehensive report on all activities conducted in the preceding period.

However, the reporting process will not rely solely on annual reports. Instead, all partners are actively encouraged and regularly reminded to maintain and update a DEC reporting table. This table will contain detailed information about each DEC activity, including stakeholder mapping (which extends beyond the primary audience to encompass unintended recipients), essential details such as timing, location, methodology, and the responsible party for each activity. Furthermore, this table will also include information relevant to WP7, specifically whether the activity was carried out in collaboration with other projects.

The ultimate goal is to ensure that DEC efforts remain transparent, comprehensive, and continuously updated, thereby fostering the efficient and effective implementation of the DEC strategy.

12 Conclusions

Deliverable 8.1, the inaugural Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plan at both the EU and National Levels, serves as the foundational blueprint for the project's strategic approach within the Climate Smart Advisors project. Its primary objective is to outline the strategies, tools, and channels that will be harnessed to achieve a multitude of DEC goals.

This comprehensive document encompasses an array of actions and approaches meticulously chosen to effectively promote project activities, disseminate valuable results, harness knowledge and solutions emerging from the project, and elevate awareness regarding the merits of Climate-Smart Farming (CSF) and the pivotal importance of climate neutrality. The journey toward these objectives will be navigated through a multifaceted approach, leveraging the dynamic capabilities of the CSA website, various social media platforms, informative newsletters, and an array of other tools and channels thoughtfully chosen to suit our purpose.

Anticipated outcomes encompass a wide array of quantifiable targets, including the number of different activities, social media followers, YouTube video views, press articles, EIP-AGRI practice abstracts, training sessions, workshops, conferences, public events, and more. It's important to note that, given the need for thorough testing to ensure maximum effectiveness, this deliverable, initially submitted in Month 6, will undergo revisions and updates at Month 24 and Month 48, potentially expanding or altering certain segments as required.

This iterative approach is pivotal because, while analytics tools can illuminate what works best, such as identifying the most effective tools or the social media posts garnering the most attention, they may not always pinpoint the exact reasons behind the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of specific approaches.

Hence, DEC revisions will be driven by the regular monitoring and evaluation process, led by BIOS as WP8, with the invaluable support of all project partners.

This document also serves as a valuable resource, offering guidelines and practical insights to all consortium members. It is our collective responsibility to contribute to the achievement of our DEC objectives, as each party plays an integral role in our shared success.

In summary, the effective management of the DEC strategy is imperative for the overall success of CSA. Through a robust DEC framework, WP8 and the entire consortium can effectively adhere to the plan, thus enhancing the potential of their endeavours to engage both existing and new audiences. Consequently, this amplification of reach significantly contributes to our ability to make a substantial impact, aligning with the objectives of the EU Climate Strategy.

Annex 1

Partners' Social Media Channels

Short Name	Legal Name	Country	Social Media	Username	Profile Link	Indicative number of followers/connections/subscribers
EV ILVO	EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK	BE	X	@ILVOvlaanderen	https://twitter.com/ILVOvlaanderen	3,241
			Linkedin	Instituut voor Landbouw-, Visserij- en Voedingsonderzoek	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ilvo/	13,000
			Facebook	Instituut voor Landbouw-, Visserij- en Voedingsonderzoek	https://www.facebook.com/InstituutVoorLandbouwEnVisserijonderzoek	2,600
			Instagram	ilvo_marien	https://www.instagram.com/ilvo_marien/?hl=en	679
			YouTube	ILVOCOMM	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwpgC4l4rnmvSACB8IMZgbg	562
ISP	INNOVATIESTEUNPUNT VOOR LANDBOUW ENPLATTELAND	BE	X	@InnoSteunpunt	https://twitter.com/InnoSteunpunt	1,184
ULIEGE	UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE	BE	X	@UniversiteLiege	https://twitter.com/UniversiteLiege	16,800
			Linkedin	University of Liège	https://www.linkedin.com/school/university-of-liege/	92,992

			Facebook	Université de Liège	https://www.facebook.com/universitedeliege	54,000
			Instagram	universitedeliege	https://www.instagram.com/universitedeliege/	15,600
			YouTube	@universitedeliege	https://www.youtube.com/@universitedeliege	57,800
ELEVEO	ELEVEO	BE	Facebook	Association Wallonne des Éleveurs	https://www.facebook.com/AssociationWallonneDesEleveurs/	11,000
LKÖ	PRASIDENTENKONFERENZ DER AT LANDWIRTSCHAFTSKAMMERN OSTERREICHS	AT	Facebook	Landwirtschaftskammer Österreich - LKÖ	https://www.facebook.com/LandwirtschaftskammerOesterreich/	812
			Instagram	lk_oesterreich	https://www.instagram.com/lk_oesterreich/	1,053
LK-STMK	LANDESKAMMER FUER LAND UND AT FORTWIRTSCHAFT IN STEIERMARK	AT	Facebook	Landwirtschaftskammer Steiermark	https://www.facebook.com/lksteiermark	14,000
			YouTube	@landwirtschaftskammersteiere8713	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCF0j7e6l0oOZvLrwjG7GBw	1,840
LK-NOE	LANDWIRTSCHAFTSKAMMER AT NIEDEROESTERREICH	AT	Instagram	unserebauernverlassdidrauf	https://www.instagram.com/unserebauernverlassdidrauf/	4,338
			Facebook	Unsere Bauern. Verlass didrauf.	https://www.facebook.com/landwirtschaftskammernoel/	28,000

			YouTube	@lk-noe	https://www.youtube.com/user/LKNOEMEDIA	636
LK-VBG	LANDWIRTSCHAFTSKAMMER VORARLBERG	AT	Facebook	Landwirtschaftskammer Vorarlberg	https://www.facebook.com/LKvorarlberg	2,400
			YouTube	@landwirtschaftskammervorar8111	https://www.youtube.com/@landwirtschaftskammervorar8111	14
NAAS	NATIONAL AGRICULTURAL ADVISORY BG SERVICE	BG	Facebook	Национална служба за съвети в земеделието	https://www.facebook.com/NAAS.BG/	2,200
			YouTube	@NAASBulgaria	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCRmAMkHEpzHXebBpoQspdvQ	6,240
UZEI	USTAV ZEMEDELSKE EKONOMIKY A INFORMACI	CZ	Facebook	ÚZEI - Ústav zemědělské ekonomiky a informací	https://www.facebook.com/uzei.cz/	781
GLZ	GRUENLANDZENTRUM NIEDERSACHEN/ BREMEN E.V.	DE	X	@GrasslandCentre	https://twitter.com/GrasslandCentre	185
			Linkedin	Grassland Centre	https://www.linkedin.com/company/gruenlandzentrum/	90
			Facebook	Grünlandzentrum	https://www.facebook.com/Gruenlandzentrum	1,000
			Instagram	gruenlandzentrum	https://www.instagram.com/gruenlandzentrum/	429
FüAk	Staatliche Führungsakademie für	DE	Facebook	Land.Schafft.Bayern	https://www.facebook.com/Land.Schafft.Bayern/	27,000

	Ernährung, Landwirtschaft und Forsten		Instagram	land.schafft.bayern	https://www.instagram.com/Land.Schafft.Bayern/	17,200
			YouTube	@stmelf	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCcv-wyjsGVhRsOYEPRwrDZw	8,540
BBG	BIOLAND BERATUNG GMBH	DE	X	@bioland_de	https://twitter.com/bioland_de	11,500
			Linkedin	Bioland e.V.	https://www.linkedin.com/company/bioland-ev/	2,113
			Facebook	Bioland	https://www.facebook.com/bioland/	37,000
			Instagram	bioland_official	https://www.instagram.com/bioland_official/	31,500
			YouTube	@Biolandkanal	https://www.youtube.com/user/Biolandkanal	6,020
ICOEL	Innovationscenter for Økologisk Landbrug P/S	DK	Facebook	Innovationscenter for Økologisk Landbrug	https://www.facebook.com/icoel.dk	1,800
			Linkedin	Innovation Centre for Organic Farming	https://www.linkedin.com/company/innovationscenter-for-%C3%B8kologisk-landbrug/	2,031
			Instagram	derforlandmand	https://www.instagram.com/derforlandmand	5,025

			YouTube	@icoeldk	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCHaRzviDuN89idgi-2ROhyA	211
ARC	POLLUMAJANDUSUURIN GUTE KESKUS EE	EE	Website	/	http://pmk.agri.ee	/
AUA	GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON	EL	Facebook	Γεωπονικό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών - Agricultural University of Athens -Official	https://www.facebook.com/AgriculturalUniversityofAthens/	7,000
			Linkedin	Agricultural University of Athens AUA OFC	https://www.linkedin.com/in/agricultural-university-of-athens-aua-ofc-3814321aa/	2,435
			Instagram	agricultural_university_athens	https://www.instagram.com/agricultural_university_athens/	2,360
			YouTube	@agriculturaluniversityofathens	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCiIRPTax6lrU8I5xY3Fie3g	683
FSH	FOODSCALE HUB GREECE ASSOCIATION EL FOR ENTREPREUNERSHIP AND INNOVATION ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA	EL	X	@FoodscaleHub	https://twitter.com/foodscalehub	3,145
			Linkedin	Foodscale Hub	https://www.linkedin.com/company/foodscale-hub/	3,145
			Facebook	Foodscale Hub	https://www.facebook.com/foodscalehub/	602
			Instagram	foodscalehub	https://www.instagram.com/foodscalehub/	250
GAIA		EL	X	@Gaia_Epexeirein	https://twitter.com/Gaia_Epexeirein	834

	GAIA EPICHEIREIN ANONYMI ETAIREIA EL PSIFIAKON YPIRESION		Linkedin	GAIA EPICHEIREIN S.A.	https://www.linkedin.com/company/gaia-epicheirein/	2,841
			Facebook	Gaia Επιχειρείν	https://www.facebook.com/gaia.epixeirein	12,000
			YouTube	@cgaiagr	https://www.youtube.com/user/cgaiagr	544
NL	NEUROPUBLIC S.A.	EL	X	@NEUROPUBLIC	https://twitter.com/neuropublic	1,475
			Linkedin	NEUROPUBLIC S.A.	https://www.linkedin.com/company/neuropublic-s-a-/	4,256
			Facebook	NEUROPUBLIC	https://www.facebook.com/neuropublic	2,100
UAL	UNIVERSIDAD DE ALMERIA	ES	X	@ualmeri	https://twitter.com/ualmeria	39,600
			Linkedin	Universidad de Almería	https://www.linkedin.com/school/universidad-de-almer-a/	42,644
			Facebook	Universidad de Almería	https://www.facebook.com/universidaddealmeria	33,000
			Instagram	unialmeria	https://www.instagram.com/unialmeria	13,200
			YouTube	@UniversidaddeAlmeriaTV	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCxlZAFiJt-QEP_Gxmt8AWAw	2,730

COEXPHAL	ASOCIACION DE ORGANIZACIONES DE ES PRODUCTORES DE FRUTAS Y HORTALIZAS DE ALMERIA	ES	X	@Coexphal	https://twitter.com/Coexphal	3,550
			Linkedin	COEXPHAL	https://www.linkedin.com/company/coexphal/	3,357
			Facebook	Coexphal	https://www.facebook.com/Coexphal	1,100
			Instagram	coexphal_	https://www.instagram.com/coexphal/	1,300
INTIA	INSTITUTO NAVARRO DE TECNOLOGIAS E ES INFRAESTRUCTURAS AGROALIMENTARIAS SA	ES	X	@IntiaSa	https://twitter.com/IntiaSa	2,739
			Linkedin	INTIA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/intia-sa/	2,018
			Facebook	INTIA	https://www.facebook.com/INTIA.NAVARRA/	1,500
			YouTube	@Intia_sa	https://www.youtube.com/@Intia_sa	833
ABERE	ABERE ZERBITZU TEKNIKOAK ES KOOPERATIBA SOZIJETATEA	ES	Website	/	http://abere.eus/index.php?idioma=es#	/
PROAGRIA	PROAGRIA KESKUSTEN LIITTO RY	FI	X	@ProAgria	https://twitter.com/proagria	5,154
			Facebook	ProAgria	https://www.facebook.com/ProAgria/	8,300

			Instagram	proagria	https://www.instagram.com/proagria/	3,885
			YouTube	@proagriavideot	https://www.youtube.com/user/proagriavideot	672
PROAGRIA EP	PROAGRIA ETELA- POHJANMAA RY	FI	X	@ProAgria	https://twitter.com/proagria	5,154
			Facebook	ProAgria	https://www.facebook.com/ProAgria/	8,300
			Instagram	proagria	https://www.instagram.com/proagria/	3,885
			YouTube	@proagriavideot	https://www.youtube.com/user/proagriavideot	672
IDELE	INSTITUT DE L'ELEVAGE	FR	X	@InstitutElevage	https://twitter.com/institutelevage	9,550
			Linkedin	Institut de l'Elevage (idele)	https://www.linkedin.com/company/institut-de-lelevage-idele/	19,844
			Facebook	Institut de l'élevage - idele	https://www.facebook.com/institutelevage	9,700
			Instagram	institutelevage	https://www.instagram.com/institutelevage/	1,958
ARVALIS		FR	X	@Arvalisofficiel	https://twitter.com/arvalisofficiel	9,708

	ARVALIS INSTITUT DU VEGETAL FR		Linkedin	ARVALIS - Institut du végétal	https://www.linkedin.com/company/arvalisinstitutduvegetal/	30,163
			Facebook	Arvalis - Couverts permanents fauchés	https://www.facebook.com/arvaliscpf	1,200
			YouTube	@TVArvalis	https://www.youtube.com/user/TVArvalis	7,350
IFIP	IFIP-INSTITUT DU PORC ASSOCIATION FR	FR	X	@IFIP_inst_porc	https://twitter.com/ifip_inst_porc?lang=fr	2,175
			Linkedin	IFIP - Institut du porc	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ifip-institut-du-porc/	4,559
			YouTube	@ifip-webtv	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCI3nOnxSPImwRwaolbZcxQA	1,550
CTIFL	CENTRE TECHNIQUE INTERPROFESSIONNEL FR DES FRUITS ET LEGUMES	FR	X	@_Ctifl	https://twitter.com/_Ctifl	2,057
			Linkedin	CTIFL	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ctifl/	11,474
			YouTube	@CtiflFrWeb	https://www.youtube.com/user/Ctifl7	726
CDA France	CHAMBRES D'AGRICULTURE FRANCE FR	FR	X	@ChambagriFrance	https://twitter.com/ChambagriFrance	17,300
			Facebook	Chambres d'agriculture	https://www.facebook.com/chambres.agriculture/	17,000

CRAB	CHAMBRE REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE DE BRETAGNE	FR	X	@ChambagriFrance	https://twitter.com/ChambagriFrance	17,300
			Facebook	Chambres d'agriculture	https://www.facebook.com/chambres.agriculture/	17,000
CRABFC	CHAMBRE REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE DEBOURGOGNE-FRANCHE-COMTE	FR	Facebook	Chambre régionale d'agriculture de Bourgogne-Franche-Comté	https://www.facebook.com/ChambagriBFC	1,100
CRANA	CHAMBRE REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE NOUVELLE - AQUITAINE	FR	YouTube	@agriculturesdenouvelle-aqu4061	https://www.youtube.com/@agriculturesdenouvelle-aqu4061	143
CRAPdL	CHAMBRE REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE DES PAYS DE LA LOIRE	FR	X	@ChambagriPdL	https://twitter.com/ChambagriPdL	3,547
			Linkedin			
			Facebook	Chambres d'agriculture des Pays de la Loire	https://www.facebook.com/Chambres.agriculture.PdL	3,400
			YouTube	@chambredagriculturePDL	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCBI1wMUIStShQ-o8eMslzgw	2,530
ELIANCE	ELIANCE	FR	X	@Eliance_Elevage	https://twitter.com/Eliance_Elevage	1,918
			Linkedin	Eliance - Des éleveurs. Une Ambition.	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eliance-elevage/	3,037

			YouTube	@eliance_elevage	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCbVq5V9VXKlo9ov3zVWciiA	34
MP	MINISTARSTVO POLJOPRIVREDE	HR	Facebook	Ministarstvo poljoprivrede	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100063739953103	11,000
			YouTube	@ministarstvopoljoprivrede8175	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdxg3qkil7q7cneXpoYf3HA	140
SZE	SZECHENYI ISTVAN EGYETEM	HU	Facebook	Széchenyi István Egyetem	https://www.facebook.com/Uni.SZE.Gyor/?locale=hu_HU	27,000
ÖMKI	OKOLOGIAI MEZOGAZDASAGI KUTATOINTEZET KOZHASZNU NONPROFIT KFT	HU	Facebook	ÖMKi - Ökológiai Mezőgazdasági Kutatóintézet	https://www.facebook.com/OMKibiokutatas/	15,000
TEAGASC	TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY	IE	X	@teagasc	https://twitter.com/teagasc	37,200
			Linkedin	Teagasc	https://www.linkedin.com/company/teagasc/	40,288
			Facebook	Teagasc	https://www.facebook.com/Teagasc	47,000
			YouTube	@TeagascMedia	https://www.youtube.com/user/TeagascMedia	16,100
ACA	ACA MEMBERS SERVICE CLG	IE	X	@aca_services	https://twitter.com/aca_services	1,404
			Facebook	A.C.A Agricultural Consultants Association	https://www.facebook.com/agriculturalconsultants/	1,400

CRPA	CENTRO RICERCHE PRODUZIONI ANIMALI-SOC. IT CONS. P. A.	IT	Website	/	https://www.crpa.it/nqcontent.cf?m?a_id=1125&tt=crpa_www&aa=chiamo&sp=crpa	/
FBS	FEDERBIO SERVIZI SRL	IT	Facebook	FederBio Servizi Srl	https://www.facebook.com/federbioservizi	308
			Linkedin	FederBio Servizi Srl	https://www.linkedin.com/company/federbioservizi/	4,318
			Instagram	federbioservizi	https://www.instagram.com/federbioservizi/	253
AIA	ASSOCIAZIONE ITALIANA ALLEVATORI	IT	Linkedin	AIA - Associazione Italiana Allevatori	https://www.linkedin.com/company/aia---associazione-italiana-allevatori/?originalSubdomain=it	1,320
Apo Conerpo	APO CONERPO SCA	IT	Website	/	https://www.apoconerpo.com/	/
CONAF	CONSIGLIO DELL'ORDINE NAZIONALE DEI DOTTORI IT AGRONOMI E FORESTALI	IT	X	@_conaf	https://twitter.com/_conaf	2,411
			Linkedin			
			Facebook	CONAF - Consiglio Ordine Nazionale Dottori Agronomi e Dottori Forestali	https://www.facebook.com/agronomiforestali/	10,000
			Instagram	ordine_agronomi_e_forestali	https://www.instagram.com/ordine_agronomi_e_forestali/	3,825

			YouTube	@ufficiostampaconaf9246	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC4LCuwlcRPhrE2mFJ8ZXtLg	174
LZUKT	VIESOJI ISTAIGA LIETUVOS ZEMES UKIO LT KONSULTAVIMO TARNYBA	LT	Facebook	Lietuvos žemės ūkio konsultavimo tarnyba	https://www.facebook.com/LZUKT/	6,700
LLKC	LATVIJAS LAUKU KONSULTACIJU UN IZGLITIBAS LV CENTRS	LV	X	@LLKC_lv	https://twitter.com/LLKC_lv	1,972
			Facebook	Latvijas Lauku konsultāciju un izglītības centrs	https://www.facebook.com/LLKCOzolnieki	8,800
			YouTube	@LLKCchannel	https://www.youtube.com/user/LLKCchannel	1,240
EUFRAS	EIROPAS LAUKSAIMNIECIBAS UN LAUKU LV KONSULTANTU ASOCIACIJA	LV	Facebook	European Forum for Agricultural and Rural Advisory Services	https://www.facebook.com/EUFRAS/	126
			LinkedIn	EUFRAS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eufRAS/	193
CONVIS	CONVIS SOCIETE COOPERATIVE LU	LU	Facebook	CONVIS	https://www.facebook.com/convis.lu	2,000
WR	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	NL	X	@WUR	https://twitter.com/WUR	45,700
			LinkedIn	Wageningen University & Research	https://www.linkedin.com/school/wageningenuniversity/	210,056
			Facebook	Wageningen University & Research	https://www.facebook.com/WUR/	112,000

			Instagram	uniwageningen	https://www.instagram.com/uniwageningen/	49,700
			YouTube	@WageningenUR	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXaytnCIAxIagIngyQh-pWg	8,520
ZLTO	ZUIDELIJKE LAND- EN TUINBOUWORGANISATIE VERENIGING	NL	X	@ZLTO	https://twitter.com/ZLTO	7,546
			Linkedin	ZLTO	https://www.linkedin.com/company/zlto/	7,387
			Facebook	ZLTO	https://www.facebook.com/zltoonline	4,000
			YouTube	@ZLTOtv	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCBfHeoxBcD15nd3umYIS4WA	699
DLV	DLV RUNDVEE ADVIES B.V.	NL	X	@DLVadvies	https://twitter.com/DLVadvies	1,171
			Linkedin	DLV Adviseurs	https://www.linkedin.com/company/dlv-advies/	4,429
			Facebook	DLV Advies	https://www.facebook.com/DLVadvies/	1,300
			YouTube	@DLVadviseurs	https://www.youtube.com/user/DLVadviseurs	407
DELPHY	DELPHY BV	NL	X	@DelphyNL	https://twitter.com/DelphyNL	2,916

			Linkedin	Delphy	https://www.linkedin.com/company/delphy/	13,698
			Facebook	Delphy	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100057365653911	1,700
			YouTube	@delphy7550	https://www.youtube.com/@delphy7550	797
CDR	CENTRUM DORADZTWA ROLNICZEGO W BRWINOWIE	PL	X	@CDR_Krakow	https://twitter.com/cdr_krakow?lang=en	11
			Facebook	Centrum Doradztwa Rolniczego Kraków	https://www.facebook.com/cdrkrakow/	1,400
KPODR	KUJAWSKO-POMORSKI OSRODEK DORADZTWA PL ROLNICZEGO W MINIKOWIE	PL	Facebook	Kujawsko-Pomorski Ośrodek Doradztwa Rolniczego	https://www.facebook.com/kpodr/?fref=ts	6,300
			YouTube	@KPODRMinikowo	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCC9bUzFo5haRN2ni9jaLz5g	1,930
WMODR	WARMINSKO-MAZURSKI OSRODEK DORADZTWA PL ROLNICZEGO Z SIEDZIBA W OLSZTYNIE	PL	Facebook	Warmińsko-Mazurski Ośrodek Doradztwa Rolniczego z siedzibą w Olsztynie	https://www.facebook.com/wmodr.olsztyn	4,400
CONSULAI	CONSULAI, CONSULTORIA AGROINDUSTRIAL LDA	PT	X	@CONSULAI	https://twitter.com/CONSULAIhttps://twitter.com/CONSULAI	272
			Linkedin	CONSULAI	https://www.linkedin.com/company/consulai/	5,595

			Facebook	CONSULAI	https://www.facebook.com/CONSULAI/	45,000
			Instagram	consulai_pt	https://www.instagram.com/CONSULAI_PT	1,475
			YouTube	@CONSULAITV	https://www.youtube.com/consulai	624
IBNA	INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE-DEZVOLTARE RO PENTRU BIOLOGIE SI NUTRITIE ANIMALA	RO	Website	/	https://www.ibna.ro/	/
USAMV CLUJ	UNIVERSITATEA DE STIINTE AGRICOLE SI MEDICINA VETERINARA CLUJ NAPOCA	RO	Linkedin	University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Cluj-Napoca	https://www.linkedin.com/company/universitatea-de-stiinte-agricole-si-medicina-veterinara-cluj-napoca/	906
			Facebook	USAMV Cluj-Napoca	https://www.facebook.com/usamvcluj	27,000
			Instagram	usamv.cluj	https://www.instagram.com/usamv.cluj/	5,105
			YouTube	@usamvcluj-napoca451	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCNymognZWeiaQrK5Xemobq	351
ADEPT	FUNDATIA ADEPT TRANSILVANIA	RO	X	@FundatiaADEPT	https://twitter.com/fundatiaadept	185
			Linkedin	Fundatia ADEPT Transilvania	https://www.linkedin.com/company/fundatia-adept-ltd/	263

			Facebook	Fundatia Adept Transilvania	https://www.facebook.com/FundatiaAdeptTransilvania/	17,000
			YouTube	@fundatiaadepttransilvania1919	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCp3nB3EiLdGN1pxs0volxzQ/featured	33
BIOSENSE	BIOSENSE INSTITUTE - RESEARCH AND RS DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTE FOR INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN BIOSYSTEMS	RS	X	@BioSenseRS	https://twitter.com/biosensers	2,106
			Linkedin	BioSense Institute	https://www.linkedin.com/company/biosense-institute/	6,081
			Facebook	BioSense Institute	https://www.facebook.com/biosense.institute/	2,700
			Instagram	biosense_institute	https://www.instagram.com/biosense_institute/	1,141
			YouTube	@biosenseinstitute8755	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCnXEiosaHvFG4nRD4zNuDKQ	150
HSH	HS HUSHALLNINGSSALLSKA PENS SERVICE SE AKTIEBOLAG	SE	X	@HSKalmar	https://twitter.com/HSKalmar	216
			Linkedin	Hushållningssällskapet	https://www.linkedin.com/company/hush-llningss-llskapens-f-rbund/	5,346
			Facebook	Hushållningssällskapet Sverige	https://www.facebook.com/hushallningssallskapetverige/	782

			YouTube	@Hushallningssallsk	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCz4I2KwR4_TRJmBFKWhzdYw	63
HSH Sjuhärad	HUSHALLNINGSSALLSKA PET SJUHARAD	SE	Facebook	Rådgivarna i Sjuhärad och Hushållningssällskapet i Sjuhärad	<a href="https://www.facebook.com/radgi
varna">https://www.facebook.com/radgi varna	1,100
HSH Jämtland	HUSHALLNINGSSALLSKA PET I JAMTLANDS	SE	Facebook	Hushållningssällskapet Jämtland	<a href="https://www.facebook.com/Hush
allningssallskapetJamtland/?loc
ale=sv_SE">https://www.facebook.com/Hush allningssallskapetJamtland/?loc ale=sv_SE	1,400
			YouTube	@hushallningssallskapetjamt 2192	<a href="https://www.youtube.com/chann
el/UCsOroygCr1mAROXDXU
GhTA">https://www.youtube.com/chann el/UCsOroygCr1mAROXDXU GhTA	20
HSH Halland	Hushållningssällskapet Halland	SE	X	@HushHalland	https://twitter.com/HushHalland	1
			Linkedin	Hushållningssällskapet Halland	<a href="https://www.linkedin.com/compa
ny/hush%C3%A5llningss%C3%
A4llskapet-halland/">https://www.linkedin.com/compa ny/hush%C3%A5llningss%C3% A4llskapet-halland/	85
			Facebook	Hushållningssällskapet	<a href="https://www.facebook.com/Hush
allningssallskapetHalland/">https://www.facebook.com/Hush allningssallskapetHalland/	2,800
			Instagram	hushallningssallskapethallan d	<a href="https://www.instagram.com/hus
hallningssallskapethalland/https:
//www.instagram.com/hushallnin
gssallskapethalland/">https://www.instagram.com/hus hallningssallskapethalland/https: //www.instagram.com/hushallnin gssallskapethalland/	831
			YouTube	@hushallningssallskapethall 9619	<a href="https://www.youtube.com/chann
el/UCpQNEIwakMR4h1QHhVG
5AQ">https://www.youtube.com/chann el/UCpQNEIwakMR4h1QHhVG 5AQ	10

KGZS	KMETIJSKO GOZDARSKA ZBORNICA SLOVENIJE	SI	Facebook	Kmetijsko gozdarska zbornica Slovenije	https://www.facebook.com/zbornicaKGZS/?locale=sr_RS	3,800
			YouTube	@zbornicaKGZS	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpy8Sn4kV9SgxHxzRLBuAuQ	364
BEC	BIOECONOMY CLUSTER	SK	X	@BE_Cluster	https://twitter.com/BE_Clusterhttps://twitter.com/BE_Cluster	35
			Linkedin	Bioeconomy Cluster	https://www.linkedin.com/company/bioeconomy-cluster-slovakia/	185
			Facebook	Bioeconomy Cluster	https://www.facebook.com/BioeconomyCluster	103
			Instagram	bioeconomycluster_sk	https://www.instagram.com/bioeconomycluster_sk/	51
OU	THE OPEN UNIVERSITY	UK	X	@OpenUniversity	https://twitter.com/openuniversity	172,900
			Facebook	The Open University	https://www.facebook.com/theopenuniversity	423,000
			Instagram	theopenuniversity	https://www.instagram.com/theopenuniversity/	79,200
			YouTube	@OpenLearn_OU	https://www.youtube.com/user/OUlearn	314,000
IfA	INNOVATION FOR AGRICULTURE	UK	X	@InnovationforAg	https://twitter.com/innovationforag	7,572

			Linkedin	Innovation for Agriculture	https://www.linkedin.com/company/innovationforagriculture/	611
			Facebook	Innovation for Agriculture - IfA	https://www.facebook.com/innovationforag/	987
			YouTube	@innovationforagriculture7779	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC9_NAR0ykcmCYMKFH1cY11Q	813
ABACUS	ABACUS AGRICULTURE LIMITED	UK	X	@abacusagri	https://twitter.com/abacusagri	1,553
ADAS	RSK ADAS LIMITED	UK	X	@ADASGroup	https://twitter.com/ADASGroup	7,396
			Linkedin	ADAS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/adas/	12,030
			Facebook	ADAS	https://www.facebook.com/ADASGroup	831
			Instagram	adas.uk	https://www.instagram.com/adas.uk/	1,252
			YouTube	@adasukltd	https://www.youtube.com/c/adasukltd	123
SRUC	SRUC	UK	X	@SRUC	https://twitter.com/SRUC	15,300
			Linkedin	SRUC	https://www.linkedin.com/school/sruc/	11,859

			Facebook	SRUC	https://www.facebook.com/sruc.ac.uk/	17,000
			Instagram	srucofficial	https://www.instagram.com/srucofficial	3,300
			YouTube	@SRUC	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCZie8fBQscdyTgmTKWnTMKA	794
DAERA	Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs	UK	X	@daera_ni	https://twitter.com/daera_ni?lang=en	13,600
			Linkedin	Department of Agriculture and Rural development, Northern Ireland Government	https://www.linkedin.com/company/department-of-agriculture-and-rural-development-northern-ireland-government/	1,687
			Facebook	Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs	https://www.facebook.com/daera.ni.gov.uk/	13,000
			Instagram	daera.ni	https://www.instagram.com/daera.ni/?hl=en	1,868
			YouTube	@DAERA-NI	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCuAcWq1MsdTcuxTWkRh9Fsw	676

Table 18 Table of Partners' Social Media Channels

National DEC Plans and Reports Template

Rectangular Snip

What online social network you will use?	Mark with "X"	Web address (-es)	Followers (count)
Facebook			
Twitter			
Instagram			
LinkedIn			
Webpage			

Please, mark the activities what you will carry out to fulfill the next requirements.

Activity	Channel	Planned times per Oct 2023-Mar20	Please mention exact channels, known
Generic Social Media Post at Partner Organization's Twitter (Text, Image, Link, Repost)	Social Media		
Generic Social Media Post at Partner Organization's LinkedIn (Text, Image, Link, Repost)	Social Media		
Mention of CSA at Partner Organization's Newsletter	E-Mail Marketing		
Press Release Issued by Partner Organization	Media		
Article Published on a National Media Outlet	Media		
Article Published on a EU Media Outlet	Media		
Article Published on a Partner Organization's Website	Website		
News Item Published on a Partner Organization's Website	Website		
CSA Presentation at External Event	Event		
Networking at External Event (Visit Card and/or Flyer and/or Poster)	Event		
Factsheet Published on a Partner Organization's Website	Website		
Factsheet Post on a Partner Organization's Twitter	Social Media		
Factsheet Post on a Partner Organization's LinkedIn	Social Media		
Practice-Oriented Abstract Published on a Partner Organization's Website	Website		
Practice-Oriented Abstract Post on a Partner Organization's Twitter	Social Media		
Practice-Oriented Abstract Post on a Partner Organization's LinkedIn	Social Media		

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